

Applications of Refractive Index in the Study of Chemical Constitution. Part II. The Constant K_r and Straight Line Mixture Law for Solid-liquid Mixtures

D. P. Joshi

The new function, K_r , has been applied for solids in a number of mixtures in the solvent benzene and also for some in the solvents like chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, aniline, and *p*-dioxane. Results are mostly appreciably applicable in accordance to the straight line mixture law in case of solutions in benzene. Small deviations occur in the results in case of the other four solvents.

In the present communication application of the new function, K_r , to mixtures, in which one of the components, the solute, is a solid, has been discussed and for which the value of $K_{r(s)}$ has been worked out from the mixture law.

The value of $K_{r(s)}$ obs. has been compared with $K_{r(s)}$ calc. obtained from atom, group, and structural values of K_r . As in the case of liquid-liquid mixtures¹, here also with non-polar solutes in the solvent benzene there is a very good agreement between observed and calculated values in most of the cases. But if one of the solvent or the solute becomes polar, deviations occur and more so if both the solvent and solute are polar. Thus the best agreement is seen in the solvent benzene, compared to results in other solvents like chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, aniline, and *p*-dioxane. In the practically non-polar solvent benzene, when the solute becomes comparatively polar as with 1-nitro-2,5-dibromo-, 1-nitro-2,5-dichloro-, and 1-nitro-2-chloro-5-bromobenzene, the deviations are marked. This is expected from theoretical considerations—the effect polarity will induce in the mixture. In these, the value obtained from solution in the case of the nearly saturated solution, however, generally agrees with the calculated value. In such cases the mean value has not been taken, nor the extrapolated value because only dilute solution can be prepared. But the value obtained from concentrated solution provides the value in agreement with the calculated one. A large number of solids were tried in the solvent benzene and some in chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, aniline, and *p*-dioxane. There is a marked difference in the deviations of the observed value from the calculated one in solvents other than benzene. In *p*-dioxane, the deviation is maximum due to the dioxane effect.

From the value of K_r obtained from solution in benzene, which affords in most cases agreeable results, the n_D^{20} of a solid can be evaluated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Laboratory chemicals of A. R. quality, either B. D. H. or Merck, were mostly used except 1-nitro-2,5-dichloro-, 1-nitro-2,5-dibromo-, 1-nitro-2-chloro-5-bromo- and *m*-dinitro-benzene which were prepared in the laboratory by the usual methods and crystallised from ethanol several times till quite pure products were obtained. The solvent, benzene

1. This issue, p. 550.

was of A. R. quality (B. D. H.) and chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, aniline, and *p*-dioxane were pure laboratory chemicals, further purified by distillation in pyrex vessels. The temperature was maintained constant at 20° within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ of the prism box of the Abbe refractometer by circulating thermostated water and that of the mixture by keeping them in the thermostat for some time before measuring the refractive index with an accuracy of ± 0.0001 .

TABLE I
Mixture in the solvent benzene.

S. No.	Solute.	$K_r(x)$ from solution.	$K_r(x)$ calc.
1.	<i>p</i> -Nitrobromobenzene	45.58 (mean)	45.48
2.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobromobenzene	Decreased from 46.30 to 45.28	45.48
3.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobromobenzene	Decreased from 45.87 to 45.25	45.48
4.	Phenol	21.35 (mean)	..
5.	<i>p</i> -Cresol	24.73 (..)	24.72 (using value of phenol)
6.	<i>o</i> -Cresol	Decreased from 24.91 to 24.60	24.72
7.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenol	38.73 (mean)	38.68
8.	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	53.19 (..)	52.99
9.	<i>p</i> -Dichlorobenzene	33.74 (..)	34.20
10.	<i>p</i> -Chlorobromobenzene	Decreased from 43.83 to 43.22	43.59
11.	<i>p</i> -Nitrochlorobenzene	35.65 (mean)	36.00
12.	<i>o</i> -Nitrochlorobenzene	35.69 (..)	36.09
13.	<i>m</i> -Nitrochlorobenzene	35.85 (..)	36.00
14.	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	37.71 (..)	37.98
15.	1-Nitro-2,5-dibromobenzene	Decreased from 63.46 to 62.76	62.81
16.	1-Nitro-2,5-dichlorobenzene	Decreased from 43.57 to 43.26	44.03
17.	1-Nitro-3-chloro-5-bromobenzene	53.14 (mean)	53.42
18.	Benzoic acid	28.12 (..)	28.31
19.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxybenzoic acid	Decreased from 31.85 to 31.45	31.57
20.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenol	Decreased from 29.25 to 28.94	29.29
21.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	Decreased from 29.62 to 28.95	29.29

TABLE II

Solute.	$K_r(x)$ from soln.	$K_r(x)$ calc.	$K_r(x)$ from soln.	$K_r(x)$ calc.
A. In chlorobenzene.			B. In nitrobenzene.	
<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	37.17 (mean)	37.98	Decreased from 37.76 to 37.38	37.38
Benzoic acid	27.95 ..	28.31	27.95 (mean)	28.31
<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	52.55 ..	52.99	52.16 (..)	52.99
C. In aniline.			D. In <i>p</i> -dioxane.	
<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	Increased from 37.27 to 38.83	37.98	Increased from 36.49 to 38.73	37.98
Benzoic acid	27.70 (Mean)	28.31	27.73	28.31
<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	Increased from 51.15 to 52.01	52.99	53.29 (mean)	52.99

The author is thankful to Dr. Shyam Sunder Joshi for his guidance.